

Synthesis of Some Local Anesthetics from 2-Phenylamino-4-Phenylthiazole

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Derivatives of 2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole have been synthesised as potential local anesthetics by treating 2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole with chloroacetyl chloride whereby chloroacetyl-2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole was obtained. This was subsequently treated with various amines to afford morpholinoacetyl, piperidinoacetyl, dimethylaminoacetyl, diethylaminoacetyl, N, N-dimethylanilino-*p*-aminoacetyl, N, N-diethylanilino-*p*-aminoacetyl, pyridine-2-aminoacetyl, pyrimidine-2-aminoacetyl, diphenylaminoacetyl, piperizinoacetyl-2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole.

SOME derivatives of 2-aminobenzothiazole^{1,8,9} and 2-aminothiazole^{4,5} are reported to possess local anesthetic activity. It was thought worthwhile to prepare some 2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole derivatives which may be used as local anesthetics. These compounds were synthesised by treatment of 2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole with chloroacetyl chloride. The chloroacetylated product so obtained was then condensed with different amines.

Preparation of Chloroacetyl-2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole(I) :

A solution of chloroacetyl chloride (2.25 g) in dry ether (20 cc) was gradually added to a solution of 2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole⁶ (5 gm) in dry ether (25 cc). The resulting mixture was worked up to give chloroacetyl-2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole m.p. 109°. Found : C, 62.21 ; H, 4.08 ; N, 8.61% ; Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₃N₂SOCl : C, 62.10 ; H, 3.95% ; N, 8.52%.

The I.R. spectrum of the compound showed absorption due to stretching frequencies of -C=O group and C-Cl bond in the region of 1690 cm⁻¹ and 740 cm⁻¹ respectively.

Condensation of Chloroacetyl-2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole with amines :

Morpholinoacetyl-2-Phenylamino-4-Phenylthiazole(II)

To a solution of chloroacetyl-2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole(I) (1.5 gm) in EtOH (2.0 ml) was added morpholine (3.5 ml). The resulting mixture was refluxed for about 4-5 hr. The excess of EtOH and morpholine were removed, residue was washed with NaHCO₃, H₂O.

The product(II) was recrystallised from 90% alcohol, m.p. 117-118°. Found : C, 65.58 ; H, 5.66 ; N, 11.17% ; Calcd for C₂₁H₂₁N₃O₂S : C, 66.49 ; H, 5.54 ; N, 11.08%.

The reaction may be depicted as

The I.R. spectrum of the compound showed absorption due to stretching frequencies of -C-N

$\begin{matrix} \text{O} \\ || \\ -\text{C}-\text{N} \end{matrix}$
group, -H₂C-O-CH₂ linkage and -C-N linkage in the region of 1675 cm⁻¹, 1190 cm⁻¹, 1110 cm⁻¹ respectively. Absorption due to stretching frequencies of thiazole nucleus lie in the region of 1580, 1460, 1340, 1030 and 810 cm⁻¹.

Similarly piperidinoacetyl, dimethylaminoacetyl, diethylaminoacetyl, N, N-dimethylanilino-*p*-aminoacetyl, N, N-diethylanilino-*p*-aminoacetyl, pyridine-2-aminoacetyl, pyrimidine-2-aminoacetyl, diphenylaminoacetyl, piperizinoacetyl-2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole were prepared. Percentage yield and m.p. are given in the table.

The hydrochlorides of these compounds were prepared by passing HCl gas into the ethereal solution of these compounds. The hydrochloride were recrystallised from 50% alcohol.

Biological Activity : The preliminary investigation on local anesthetic activity of hydrochlorides of Morpholinoacetyl-2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole, Piperidinoacetyl-2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole and Diethylaminoacetyl-2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole in 2% solution show surface anaesthesia for 30, 32 and 26 minutes respectively on rabbit cornea while the cocain (in 2% solution) shows surface anaesthesia for 38 minutes.

TABLE

S. No.	Name of the compounds	Yield %	M. P. °C	Formula ^a	M. P. °C (Hydrochloride)
1.	Morpholinoacetyl-PT ^b	62.0	117-118	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ SO ₂	168-169
2.	Piperidinoacetyl-PT	60.3	126-127	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ SO	173-174
3.	Dimethylaminoacetyl-PT	63.1	135-136	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ SO	172-173
4.	Diethylaminoacetyl-PT	59.5	131-132	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ SO	176-177
5.	N : N-dimethylanilino- <i>p</i> -aminoacetyl-PT	51.7	121-122	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ SO	181-182
6.	N : N-diethylanilino- <i>p</i> -aminoacetyl-PT	50.0	124-125	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ N ₃ SO	189
7.	Pyridine-2-aminoacetyl-PT	61.5	122-123	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₄ SO	166-167
8.	Pyrimidine-2-aminoacetyl-PT	63.0	119-120	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₅ SO	170-171
9.	Diphenylaminoacetyl-PT	60.8	114-115	C ₂₉ H ₂₃ N ₃ SO	178-179
10.	Piperizinoacetyl-PT	65.6	139	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₄ SO	192-198

^a All the compounds were analysed for N, S and gave satisfactory analytical results.

^b PT stands for 2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole.

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